

Extractivist Dynamics in the BRICS Commodity Trade: profit shifting, export triangulation, and the potential of tax cooperation

Giulia Busato dos Santos

Abstract

Economic cooperation among BRICS countries has expanded significantly over the past two decades, particularly through the rapid growth of intra-bloc trade. However, this economic integration has not been matched by equivalent progress in tax governance. Given the continued prominence of commodities in BRICS trade, this gap raises important questions regarding the distribution of value generated through natural resource extraction. This article examines how financial mechanisms such as profit shifting and export triangulation reproduce extractive dynamics within BRICS commodity trade. Drawing on debates on extractivism and financialization, it argues that these corporate practices enable multinational firms to relocate profits away from producing economies, limiting the fiscal benefits derived from resource extraction. Empirically, the analysis combines a conceptual review with secondary data from the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development and Instituto Justiça Fiscal. The findings suggest that both the OECD-led BEPS framework and existing BRICS tax cooperation remain insufficient to regulate profit shifting, highlighting the need for stronger fiscal coordination to improve the capture of resource rents in producing economies.

Keywords: Extractivism; Profit shifting; Commodity trade; BRICS tax cooperation

Introduction

Economic cooperation among BRICS+ members has expanded significantly over the past two decades. Trade-weighted bilateral tariffs have declined since the early 2000s, reflecting increasing economic integration and dialogue on issues such as supply chains, trade facilitation and WTO reform, although policy cooperation remains relatively shallow (UNCTAD, 2026). Despite this growing integration, one structural feature continues to define the bloc's economic relations: the central role of commodities in intra-BRICS+ trade (UNCTAD, 2026). This pattern reflects the historical trajectories of many member states as countries of the Global South, whose integration into the global economy has long been associated with the extraction and export of natural resources.

The persistence of commodity dependence can be understood through the extractivism debate, which gained prominence in Latin America in the 2010s. Scholars such as Eduardo Gudynas, Alberto Acosta and Maristella Svampa conceptualized neo-extractivism as a development model based on the large-scale extraction of natural resources for export, historically rooted in colonial patterns of dependency and uneven development. More recent scholarship has expanded this concept beyond national development models to examine how extractivist dynamics operate across global production networks, highlighting broader circuits of value appropriation along supply chains (Arboleda, 2019).

Contemporary approaches further emphasize the connection between extractivism and financialization. Mechanisms of rent extraction and “value grabbing” allow capital to appropriate wealth generated in resource-producing regions through financial and corporate structures, reinforcing new forms of dependency within global capitalism (Andreucci et al., 2017; Paulani, 2022). In this configuration, commodity-producing economies frequently retain the environmental and social costs associated with extraction while a significant share of financial returns is captured elsewhere. These dynamics can be interpreted as a form of financial extractivism, in which value generated through natural resource production is transferred away from producing economies through mechanisms embedded in global trade and corporate networks.

Within BRICS commodity trade, practices such as export triangulation and profit shifting by transnational corporations may represent concrete mechanisms through which these extractive circuits operate. While production remains located in resource-rich economies, profits can be relocated to low-tax jurisdictions, limiting the fiscal benefits captured by producing states and reinforcing dependency within the global political economy. In this context, strengthening fiscal coordination among BRICS members emerges as a potential tool to address these asymmetries. This raises an important question: to what extent do profit shifting and export triangulation reproduce extractive dynamics in BRICS commodity trade, and could greater tax cooperation among BRICS countries mitigate these effects?

To address this question, the article combines a conceptual analysis—drawing on the

literature on extractivism, financialization and BRICS cooperation—with an empirical examination of secondary data from reports by UNCTAD and Instituto Justiça Fiscal on the last two decades of intra-BRICS trade. It argues that these financial practices function as extensions of extractive dynamics by enabling the transfer of commodity rents away from producing economies, and suggests that enhanced tax cooperation within BRICS could help address these dynamics by improving transparency and coordination in the trade relations of developing economies.

Financial Mechanisms of Extractivism

In commodity trade, multinational firms frequently employ financial and logistical arrangements that allow profits to be recorded outside the countries where resources are extracted. This session therefore shall explain the working of these operations as well as the degree of their relation to financial extractive dynamics impacting commodity trade within the BRICS. One common mechanism pointed out by Instituto Justiça Fiscal (2024) as an agent of profit shifting and consequently tax base erosion is export triangulation, in which commodities are formally exported to an intermediary trading subsidiary located in a low-tax jurisdiction before being sold to the final buyer.

To illustrate this dynamic, consider a producer operating in its home country, where corporate profits are taxed under the jurisdiction of the producing state. Multinational firms can reduce their tax liabilities by structuring transactions through affiliated intermediary companies located in lower-tax jurisdictions. Instead of selling commodities directly to the final buyer at market price, the producer sells them at an artificially low price to a trading subsidiary abroad. Because this transaction is recorded domestically, the producing company reports smaller profits and therefore pays lower taxes. The intermediary company then resells the commodity at the full market price, capturing the difference as profit in the lower-tax jurisdiction (Instituto Justiça Fiscal, 2024).

As a result, a significant portion of the value generated through the extraction and export of natural resources is recorded outside the producing economy. While the physical production and associated costs remain in the home country, the profits—and therefore the taxation of those profits—are relocated abroad. In this sense, mechanisms such as export triangulation and profit shifting enable the displacement of resource rents, allowing firms to capture a greater share of the surplus generated by commodity production while eroding the tax base of producing states. Consequently, wealth derived from resource extraction does not fully translate into domestic fiscal revenue or national income, limiting the capacity of governments to recover public investments in sectors such as agriculture or mining (Instituto Justiça Fiscal, 2024).

Empirical trade patterns illustrate the relevance of these mechanisms. A significant share of commodity exports from major producers is formally recorded as destined for global trading hubs rather than final consumer markets. For instance, commodities exported from

countries such as Brazil are frequently routed through intermediary jurisdictions such as Switzerland or Singapore, where multinational trading firms concentrate their commercial operations. For Brazil, depending on the product, over 90% of the exports are made intra-group, meaning they are made between transnational companies with intermediation abroad (Instituto Justica Fiscal, 2024). This pattern reflects the central role of intermediary trading entities in global commodity markets and creates opportunities for profit shifting through transfer pricing arrangements.

While these financial arrangements are often discussed primarily as mechanisms of tax avoidance, they also have broader implications for the political economy of commodity production. By relocating profits away from producing economies, these practices reshape where the rents generated through natural resource extraction are ultimately captured. This dynamic invites interpretation through the lens of extractivism and value capture as to a high degree it enables multinational firms to appropriate resource rents generated in commodity-producing economies, transforming what would otherwise constitute public revenue into privately captured offshore profits.

Extractivism And Value Capture

As the debate on neo-extractivism advances, increasing attention has been given to the expansion of global capitalism and the central role of financialization, sometimes overshadowing its persistent connection to resource dependency (Andreucci et al., 2017). Yet, although capitalism has modernized its mechanisms of accumulation through financialization and more virtual forms of exploitation (Paulani, 2022), extraction remains a constitutive feature of contemporary capitalist operations (Gago; Mezzadra, 2017, p. 579).

Within this framework, the concept of resource rent becomes central. Resource rents refer to the economic surplus generated from natural resources, defined as the difference between the market value of a resource and the costs of its extraction and production (OECD, 2008, p. 465). Because these rents derive from control over scarce natural assets, they become key objects of competition and appropriation within global commodity markets. From this perspective, contemporary capitalism has not abandoned resource dependency but has reorganized around mechanisms through which value is appropriated through rent extraction rather than productive transformation (Strauss, 2009 apud Andreucci et al., 2017, p. 2).

Building on this approach, political ecology scholars have developed the concept of value grabbing to describe situations in which institutional arrangements and property rights enable actors to appropriate value generated elsewhere through rent relations (Andreucci et al., 2017). Rather than accumulation through production, this perspective highlights how economic surplus is captured through the control of infrastructures, legal frameworks, and market access points that redirect value flows across global economic networks.

This dynamic is particularly relevant for commodity-reliant economies such as the BRICS+, often characterized as “nature-exporting societies,” where resource rents represent an important source of public revenue (UNCTAD, 2026). Because extraction occurs domestically, states invest heavily in infrastructure and in managing environmental externalities associated with export-oriented production, expecting to capture part of the resulting rents through taxation (Andreucci et al., 2017, p. 3). However, when transnational firms control trade infrastructures and legal arrangements within commodity supply chains, profits can be shifted abroad, limiting the fiscal benefits captured by producing economies.

These dynamics cannot be understood solely as tax avoidance. Rather, they reflect processes through which resource rents generated in producing territories are appropriated elsewhere, disproportionately affecting developing economies. In this sense, such financial arrangements constitute forms of value grabbing, allowing actors positioned in global commodity networks to capture the economic surplus generated through extraction beyond the territories where it originates.

Limits of Current Tax Governance

These practices are widely discussed in the literature on Base Erosion and Profit Shifting (BEPS) promoted by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. Although BEPS represents the main international effort to address profit shifting by multinational corporations, its institutional centrality has also drawn criticism. The strong predominance of the OECD in global tax governance has often been seen as reflecting the interests of advanced economies and has proven insufficient to address financial extraction mechanisms linked to commodity trade, highlighting the need to analyze international taxation from a peripheral perspective (Instituto Justiça Fiscal, 2024).

Meanwhile, trade among BRICS economies has expanded rapidly over the past two decades. The report *Two Decades of Intra-BRICS Trade: Trends, Patterns and Policies*, published by the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, shows that intra-BRICS trade increased from about US\$84.2 billion in 2003 to US\$1.17 trillion in 2024 (UNCTAD, 2026, p. 1). This growth reflects the consolidation of South–South trade networks and growing economic interdependence among member states. However, because commodity exports remain central to several BRICS economies, governments rely heavily on taxation of natural-resource sectors to capture part of the economic surplus generated through extraction.

Despite this expanding trade integration, institutional coordination has evolved more slowly. BRICS cooperation has largely taken the form of dialogue and soft coordination—particularly on multilateral trade governance and WTO reform—while structural barriers such as regulatory differences, institutional capacity gaps, and geopolitical divergences continue to limit deeper policy integration (UNCTAD, 2026, pp. 72–74). As a result, formal coordination in tax policy remains limited, especially regarding multinational corporations operating across commodity supply chains.

These dynamics reveal important limitations in the current international tax framework. Global tax governance remains largely shaped by OECD institutions, where developing economies—many of them commodity exporters—have comparatively limited influence in rule-making processes. This imbalance contributes to regulatory gaps in sectors central to the fiscal sustainability of many developing countries.

Recent policy discussions within BRICS indicate growing awareness of these limitations. In a joint statement issued in 2025, BRICS finance ministers supported the creation of a United Nations Framework Convention on International Tax Cooperation, emphasizing the need for a more inclusive global tax architecture that strengthens transparency, mutual assistance, and the fair allocation of taxing rights.

At the same time, existing BRICS tax cooperation remains largely focused on technical dialogue and information exchange rather than binding regulatory mechanisms capable of addressing profit-shifting practices in commodity trade.

Taken together, these dynamics reveal a structural mismatch between the economic realities of intra-BRICS trade and the architecture of current tax governance. While trade flows among BRICS countries have expanded rapidly and remain strongly dependent on natural resource exports, both international tax frameworks and internal BRICS cooperation mechanisms remain limited in their ability to regulate profit shifting in commodity markets. Consequently, multinational firms can exploit jurisdictional differences to relocate profits through intermediary trading hubs, capturing part of the resource rents generated in producing economies and reproducing extractive dynamics through financial and corporate mechanisms.

Potential for BRICS Tax Cooperation

While current tax governance frameworks show significant limitations in addressing profit shifting within commodity trade, recent discussions among BRICS countries suggest the potential for stronger forms of fiscal coordination capable of mitigating these dynamics. In particular, policy debates have increasingly emphasized the need to move beyond existing mechanisms of dialogue and technical exchange toward more concrete regulatory measures.

The report produced by Instituto Justiça Fiscal highlights several areas in which deeper cooperation could strengthen the capacity of commodity-exporting economies to capture resource rents. Among these are enhanced information exchange between tax authorities, improved monitoring of intra-group commodity transactions, and greater transparency regarding the role of intermediary trading companies in global commodity chains (Instituto Justiça Fiscal, 2024, pp. 4–6). Such measures would make it easier to identify price manipulation practices associated with export triangulation and transfer pricing strategies.

In addition, the report suggests that cooperation between major trading partners —

particularly large commodity exporters and importers within the BRICS framework—could improve oversight of commodity supply chains and reduce opportunities for profit shifting through intermediary jurisdictions (Instituto Justiça Fiscal, 2024, p. 6). Coordinated approaches to transfer-pricing enforcement and shared tax information could therefore play an important role in limiting the relocation of profits generated through resource extraction.

Recent policy statements by BRICS governments (2025) also point toward broader institutional reform. In 2025, BRICS finance ministers expressed support for the establishment of a United Nations Framework Convention on International Tax Cooperation, emphasizing the importance of fair allocation of taxing rights, transparency, and effective cooperation in combating illicit financial flows. Taken together, these proposals suggest that stronger forms of coordination—moving beyond voluntary dialogue toward more institutionalized cooperation—may be necessary if BRICS countries are to effectively address the mechanisms through which resource rents generated in commodity-producing economies are shifted abroad and historically extractivist exploratory dynamics are reproduced.

Conclusion

In sum, the analysis suggests that profit shifting and export triangulation function as contemporary mechanisms through which extractive dynamics are reproduced within BRICS commodity trade. Although natural resources are physically extracted in producing economies, the financial architecture of global commodity markets enables a significant share of the resulting resource rents to be captured elsewhere through corporate and fiscal arrangements. By relocating profits to intermediary jurisdictions and trading hubs, multinational firms effectively transform domestic economic surplus into offshore gains, limiting the fiscal capacity of producing states and reinforcing asymmetric patterns of value capture in the global political economy. The rapid expansion of intra-BRICS trade over the past two decades has intensified the importance of this issue, yet current tax governance—dominated by initiatives such as the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development's BEPS framework—remains insufficient to address profit shifting in commodity sectors that are central to many BRICS economies. At the same time, tax cooperation within the bloc has so far remained largely limited to dialogue and technical exchange. Strengthening fiscal coordination among BRICS countries therefore represents a potential pathway to mitigate these dynamics. Measures such as enhanced transparency in commodity trading, coordinated transfer-pricing enforcement, and deeper institutional cooperation could improve the capacity of producing economies to capture resource rents generated through extraction. In this sense, advancing more robust forms of BRICS tax cooperation may not only address fiscal losses associated with profit shifting but also contribute to challenging the financial mechanisms through which contemporary forms of extractivism continue to operate within global commodity markets.

Bibliographical References

ANDREUCCI, Diego; GARCÍA-LAMARCA, Melissa; WEDEKIND, Jonah; SWYNGEDOUW, Erik. “Value grabbing”: a political ecology of rent. Capitalism Nature Socialism, London, 2017.

ARBOLEDA, Martín. From spaces to circuits of extraction: value in process and the mine/city nexus. Capitalism Nature Socialism, London, 2019.

BRICS. BRICS joint statement in support of the United Nations Framework Convention on International Tax Cooperation. Brasília, July 2025. Available at: <https://tax.brics.br/>. Accessed on: 13 Mar. 2026.

BRICS TAX COOPERATION PLATFORM. BRICS tax cooperation. 2025. Available at: <https://tax.brics.br/>. Accessed on: 13 Mar. 2026.

GAGO, Verónica; MEZZADRA, Sandro. A critique of the extractive operations of capital: toward an expanded concept of extractivism. Rethinking Marxism, London, v. 29, n. 4, p. 574-591, 2017.

Instituto Justiça Fiscal. Exportações de commodities: prejuízo no Brasil e lucros em paraísos fiscais – propostas de solução. 2024. Available at: <https://ijf.org.br>. Accessed on: 13 Mar. 2026.

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. OECD glossary of statistical terms. 2008. Available at: <https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/>. Accessed on: 13 Mar. 2026.

PAULANI, Leda Maria. A dependência revisitada: relações de troca, a fase 4.0 e o caso do Brasil. Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Economia Política, Rio de Janeiro, n. 64, Sep.-Dec. 2022.

United Nations Conference on Trade and Development. Two decades of intra-BRICS trade: trends, patterns and policies. 2026. Available at: <https://unctad.org/publication/two-decades-intra-brics-trade-trends-patterns-and-policies>. Accessed on: 13 Mar. 2026.